

PROMISING POTENTIAL FOR INDIAN HOSPITALITY INDUSTRY WITH SPECIAL REFERENCE TO DELHI NCR- AN OUTLOOK

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ABSTRACT

Today, the Indian hospitality industry has risen as one of the key drivers of development among the service sector segment in India. The Tourism industry in India has huge potential considering the rich social and chronicled legacy, assortment in biology, territories and spots of common magnificence spread over the nation. Tourism Industry in India is not only a important source of FDI but also becoming a potential segment for generating jobs within the country. One side there is lot of lucrative opportunities for the Indian players to invest in the sector and on the other side it offers various challenges in terms of extensive business environment, changing preferences variable cost, availability of skilled staff, land cost, energy cost, licensing policies, taxation policies and so on, which present difficulty in survival of existing players and hindrance in entrance of new players. There these difficulties need to be addressed and taken care off. This paper examines the challenges and opportunities faced by the hospitality industry and also analyzing various growth drivers in the sector and the forces act as game changers in spite of various challenges.

Key- Words: NCR, Hospitality, FDI, Skilled staff.

INTRODUCTION

In this research paper, we give an appraisal of the different dangers and difficulties lying ahead for the hospitality business in accomplishing ideal execution from their hotel resources.

If the economic situations were to additionally disintegrate, and signs are that they will, there will be a noteworthy effect on interest development, income execution and productivity of hotel organizations. Performance stress will keep on driving industry players to investigate more productive plans of action and manufacture new associations. The business will leave upon an adventure of solidification and we could observe transformations, mergers and acquisitions, more out of impulses than out of decision.

A new arrangement of aggressive pressure through adjustment in the demand & supply irregularity will go ahead to enhanced decisions and lead to discontinuity of interest. Further, the overall reduce speed of monetary movement will directly affect demand crosswise over fragments and feeder markets. Organizations are probably going to embrace stringent somberness measures and optional spends on movement will be a certain injured individual. These measures are probably going to disintegrate demand, realize considerable rate correction, defend spends on MICE occasions and lead to sub-ideal income exhibitions crosswise over hotels.

The official administration at hotels should continually improve and embrace dynamic business practices to achieve intrinsic adaptability in working cost structures. While lodgings have just streamlined key fixed input costs like payroll and raw materials proceeded with enhancements will be hard to get a hold of and thus visitor fulfillment levels and representative assurance will be contrarily affected. The commodity price cycle has officially bottomed out and a powerless precipitation is probably going to additionally fuel expansion prompting increment in normal administration cost for each involved room. Innovations in supply chain management and outsourcing will become crucial and would have to be focused upon. Customization, re-arrangement and re-designing of procedures will assume a crucial job in deciding the degree to which an organization is adapted operationally to deliver steady profitability.

The quickly changing macroeconomic condition and rationalization in asset values will give alluring chances of acquisitions of hotel assets. Notwithstanding, to use open doors for development and extension, it will be important to concentrate on prompt upgrades in the soundness of the organization's balance sheet. A key test would be the usage of obligation rebuilding methodology and plan for long-term capital accessibility

Key Game Changers:

- Emergence of secondary and tertiary cities
- Emergence of micro-markets
- Continued marketing of Brand India
- Continued improvement of infrastructure in Indian cities and towns
- Ease of attaining Indian visas

- Development of India's image as a safe, secure and friendly destination
- Development and marketing of niche tourism like medical tourism, religious circuits, adventure tourism etc.

The Maturing of Indian Hotel Markets

In the year 2000, hospitality in India was primarily dominated by the domestic players, namely Taj Group of Hotels, Oberoi Hotels & Resorts, ITC Hotels, and the government owned ITDC (The India Tourism Development Corporation Ltd) Hotels, with only a handful of international brands having a token presence in the form of marketing alliances in India. Also, while some of today's home-grown hotel chains like Leela, Bharat Hotels, Sarovar and Asian Hotels were around at that time, they were for the most part single-asset owners. There was a perception that India was a tough place for foreign companies to do business in and that a strong local presence with excellent contacts was required to be able to penetrate this market. Additionally, several businesses and consequently most international brands were more focused on fast-growing markets in the Middle East and China, which offered more opportunities for growth at that time. Additionally, the emergence of a branded budget and economy segment presents tremendous opportunities and will attract many new players to an India going forward.

About 10 years back, there were extremely just a bunch of real hotel markets in India, specifically the four metros and conceivably a Bangalore or a Goa, a consequence of organizations fundamentally being situated in and requiring lodgings in these urban communities. In this way, while guests to these real urban areas had a decision of a few extravagance and upscale lodgings, subsidiary with both household and universal brands, the accessibility and nature of inns declined essentially when daring to the littler urban areas.

In the most recent decade, as the real urban communities grew quickly, land costs took off, and the expense of setting up and supporting business activities in these urban communities ended up restrictive. Organizations, in this manner, began taking a gander at different urban areas in the nation where costs were bring down which brought about the rising of urban communities, for example, Hyderabad, Pune, Jaipur and Ahmedabad. Because of these elements,

there are right now around 10 to 12 primary inn showcases in the nation, all of which offer an assortment of marked item contributions crosswise over various positioning. The rise of these optional and tertiary urban areas prompted a forceful increment in hotel industry advancement movement and gave roads to extension of hotel brands, which were already reliant on new open doors in simply the five primary urban communities.

Another pattern that has now developed in the different real markets is the development of miniaturized scale markets, particularly in the essential urban areas. As drives in bigger urban areas are progressively estimated in measure of movement time as opposed to separate, individuals are remaining at lodgings that are found nearer to their work environment, along these lines sparing urgent travel time that may somehow have been squandered in rush hour gridlock. In this way, while it may have been practical beforehand to construct just a single Holiday Inn or one Marriott in the market, the nearness of autonomous smaller scale advertises now permits the presence of numerous inns with a similar brand alliance without fears of cannibalization of interest.

The Ministry of Tourism's 'Mind boggling India' battle has begun to hit home and will probably assume its job in expanding appearances to India. That being stated, the general assumption is that in spite of the fact that India has a changed bundle of goals to offer, moderately unremarkable endeavors have been made to showcase Brand India. The fate of the Indian markets and their capacity to develop into goals depends on deliberate endeavors, both by the applicable government bodies and the private part players. Innovativeness will be of substance and maybe the time has come to begin advertising Brand India under a few subsets, for example, social the travel industry, eco-accommodating traveling, medicinal the travel industry, religious circuits, experience sports the travel industry, natural life safaris, shoreline goals and wellbeing excursions.

Key Game Changers:

- Emergence of auxiliary and tertiary urban communities
- Emergence of miniaturized scale markets
- Continued advertising of Brand India
- Continued enhancement of framework in Indian urban areas and towns
- Ease of achieving Indian visas

- Development of India's picture as a protected, secure and inviting goal
- Development and advertising of specialty the travel industry like therapeutic the travel industry, religious circuits, experience the travel industry and so on.

The monetary downturn, toward the start of the decade, prompted a change in perspective among these organizations as they could never again depend entirely on the more developed economies and they began measuring the huge open doors that a nation like India brought to the table. The way that India was less affected by the worldwide downturns - one toward the start of the decade and the other toward its finish - when contrasted with whatever remains of the world has insistently demonstrated the intrinsic quality of the Indian economy and its buyer base of over a billion people. As Indians voyaged all the more as often as possible around the globe, they encountered worldwide inn marks direct, because of which these brands delighted in more prominent acknowledgment and acknowledgment in India. Also, as universal appearance to India expanded, the remote brands were better set to draw in these guests because of their solid reservations arranged the world over. With the proceeded with development in India's GDP, enhancement in the per capita pay, and expanded optimistic spending, the Indian friendliness division is required to become quicker than most nations around the globe. Most significant lodging brands, for example, Starwood, Hilton, Marriott, Hyatt and Accor as of now have a developing nearness in India and they have a much more grounded pipeline. Furthermore, the rise of a marked spending plan and economy fragment presents gigantic chances and will pull in numerous new players to an India going ahead.

Key Game Changers:

- Entry of most significant global brands
- Changing view of Indian markets as a worthwhile open door among worldwide brands
- Growth of the Indian white collar class offering a huge customer base of in excess of 1 billion individuals
- Educated and very much uncovered Indian groups of onlookers, prone to acknowledge worldwide brands wholeheartedly
- Expected development of marked spending plan and economy lodgings

4. Hotel Development Costs:

In the previous ten years most ware costs have gone up. Advancement costs have dependably been a test for anybody hoping to assemble a lodging in India. The land cost has progressively turned into a noteworthy part of the advancement cost for any venture, representing 30-half of the aggregate improvement cost, while the equivalent likens to around 15-20% globally. The high thickness of improvement inside Indian urban areas and the lack of empty land bundles appropriate for lodgings had prompted forceful offering wars among planned purchasers and constrained costs upwards. With the expanded pace of development movement around the globe, particularly in the Middle East and China, the cost of development material, for example, steel and cement expanded steeply as of late. While this was counterbalanced by sourcing furniture and installations from China by a few late lodging activities, the extra concern in regards to the nature of Chinese merchandise is one that now should be tended to.

HVS sees that inns worked in India regularly surpass the brand determinations that may exist for these brands globally and that designers frequently will in general spend more cash on their inns than required. A normal mid-showcase business inn in the US or Europe, in this way, does not cost so a lot to build as it does in India.

The extensive lumbering procedure of getting licenses and allows and development defers serves to build costs much more. Since its getting late and cost engaged with working through every one of these issues lastly opening an inn, engineers who figured out how to do as such were not keen on moving their inns or requested costs that were far in abundance of substitution cost. As we investigate the following ten years, we trust that insofar as asking costs remain fundamentally higher than the swap cost for the item, designers and financial specialists will manufacture as opposed to purchase.

Table No-1: Typical Development Cost per Key (INR)

Positioning	Typical Development Cost per Key (INR)
Luxury	12,500,000 and above
Upper Upscale	8,500,000 to 12,500,000
Upscale	6,000,000 to 8,500,000
Mid Market	3,500,000 to 5,500,000
Budget	2,500,000 to 3,500,000
Economy	2,500,000 and below

Key Game Changers

- Likely justification of land costs, because of the ongoing financial conditions
- Increased import of material from worldwide sources, as long as quality merchandise are accessible
- Expected defense of expenses, with government intercession in loosening up the permit procedure
- Expected justification of per key advancement costs, with section of brands over all positioning

Objective of Research

To study and analyze the growth drivers and game changers of hospitality industry in India

To analyze future challenges and opportunities for hospitality industry in India

Research Methodology

Secondary data is used for the research in the form of various research articles, whitepapers, magazines, project works & internet.

ANALYSIS

Opportunities for Hospitality and Travel Industry in India

From the data it is clear that hospitality industry in India is heading towards great opportunities in terms of **Robust demand**- It is expected that arrival of international tourist will reach up to 30.5 million by 2018

India can explore various opportunities in terms of art, sports, film, rural and religious tourism.

Government support : under various initiative taken the GOI many cities are been considered as heritage asset and funds is been released for their modification and renovation which will attract more tourist to the places

Figure No:-1- Meeting, Incentive, Conference and exhibitions

Estimation of market size

India is the most digitally-advanced traveller nation in terms of digital tools being used for planning, booking and experiencing a journey, India's rising middle class and increasing disposable incomes has continued to support the growth of domestic and outbound tourism.

Foreign Tourist Arrivals (FTAs) increased to 8.36 million in January-October 2018, achieving a growth rate of 6.20 per cent year-on-year.

The travel & tourism sector in India accounted for 8 per cent of the total employment opportunities generated in the country in 2017, providing employment to around 41.6 million people during the same year. The number is expected to rise by 2 per cent annum to 52.3 million jobs by 2028.

International hotel chains are increasing their presence in the country, as it will account for around 47 per cent share in the Tourism & Hospitality sector of India by 2020 & 50 per cent by 2022

Figure No:- 2 Contribution of Tourism and Hospitality to GDP

Fig:-3 contribution of travel and Tourism total contribution

Analysis: Investment

During the period April 2000-June 2018, the hotel and tourism sector attracted around US\$ 11.39 billion of FDI, according to the data released by Department of Industrial Policy and Promotion (DIPP).

Fig No:- 4 Segment wise Revenue Share

Fig:- 5 Expected Segment wise revenue share

Key Trends

The Indian government has realised the country's potential in the tourism industry and has taken several steps to make India a global tourism hub.

Some of the major initiatives planned by the Government of India to give a boost to the tourism and hospitality sector of India are as follows:

- Statue of Sardar Vallabhbhai Patel, also known as 'State of Unity', was inaugurated in October 2018. It is the highest standing statue in the world at a height of 182 metre. It is expected to boost the tourism sector in the country and put India on the world tourism map.
- The Government of India is working to achieve 1 per cent share in world's international tourist arrivals by 2020 and 2 per cent share by 2025.

Under Budget 2018-19, the government has allotted Rs 1,250 crore (US\$ 183.89 million) for Integrated development of tourist circuits under Swadesh Darshan and Pilgrimage Rejuvenation and Spiritual Augmentation Drive (PRASAD)

Fig- 6 Revenue collected from foreign Tourist

Fig- 7 Expected revenue collected from Foreign Tourist upto 2020

The prospects for the lodging business in India are splendid. With recovery in the worldwide economy, universal vacationer inflow into the nation is relied upon to rise. Also, facilitating of universal games occasions and exchange fairs and shows in the nation are relied upon to help both inflow of worldwide vacationers and household visitor development.

The up and coming mechanical parks, producing offices and ports the nation over give a decent chance to spending plan and mid-advertise lodgings. Despite the fact that around 89,500 extra rooms are relied upon to come up in India in the following five years, the supply of

marked/quality rooms in India is much lower contrasted with different nations over the globe. Thus, there exists colossal potential for financial specialists and administrators over every one of the sections of lodging industry in India. The expansion in room inventories is required to make the inn business more focused and lodgings would be experiencing tension to keep up quality and administration levels at aggressive costs. Aggressive valuing among the marked inns alongside the expansion of more spending plan and mid-advertise lodgings would make the inn business cost focused with different goals. This would help the development of fragments, for example, MICE, among others.

1. **High discretionary cashflow:** With the light development in the Indian economy, the Indian white collar class has higher extra cash. This has been recognized, by about 94% of the respondents as a key factor for the expanded local travel the nation over.

2. **Appearance of new areas:** the expanded interest would originate from new areas generally because of better access and enhanced foundation. Accordingly, a huge supply is being created and liable to create at such areas All classes are under served now of time. In spite of the fact that there are less urban communities where you can have five-star inns however a lot bigger number of urban communities with more prominent potential for spending class inns in India. Reasonableness and nature of experience are enter factors in characterizing this move far from five star to more spending class inns.

3. **Stead fastness projects and advancement:** Although voyagers esteem unwaveringness programs and limited time plots, our overview members don't consider it to be a key determinant in choosing their settlement. Different components that are adding to the development in local the travel industry incorporate access to online travel and lodging appointments.

Organizations need to Build efficiencies and set up methodologies to grow which they are doing .They are taking activities to manufacture efficiencies in their present tasks. Better administration of expenses is at the highest point of the motivation.. The expensive activities to lessen costs incorporate the accompanying:

- Converting settled expenses to variable: Increase extent of non-contracted work and re-appropriate back-end tasks.

- Reducing vitality costs: Eliminate inefficient utilization and receive 'green' building strategies.
- Managing labor costs: Train representatives over various abilities, put resources into innovation, investigate redistributing and oversee wearing down better.

Hospitality industry faces some inherent challenges as illustrated below:

1. **High irregularity:** The Indian lodging industry typically encounters appeal amid October–April, pursued which the storm months involve low interest. Normally the December and March quarters get 60% of the year's turnover for India's hoteliers. Be that as it may, this pattern is seeing a change over the ongoing couple of years. Lodgings have acquainted different contributions with enhance execution (inhabitation) amid the lean months. These incorporate focusing on the conferencing portion and offering worthwhile bundles amid the lean time frame.

2. **Labour concentrated:** Quality of labor is imperative in the accommodation business. The business gives work to gifted, semi-talented, and untalented work straightforwardly and in a roundabout way. In India, the normal representative to-room proportion at 1.6 (2008-09), is a lot higher than that for lodgings over the world. The proportion remains at 1.7 for five-star lodgings and at 1.9 and 1.6 for the four-star and three-star classes individually. Inn proprietors in India tend to "over-spec" their lodgings, prompting higher labor necessity. With the passage of marked worldwide inns in the Indian business crosswise over various classifications, Indian lodging organizations need to wind up more labor effective and reevaluate their staffing prerequisites. In the event of Mid market brands like Keys we run the ship on a proportion of 0.7 to 1

3. **Fragmented:** The Indian inn industry is exceedingly divided with an expansive number of little and disorderly players representing a lion's offer.

4. **Huge forthright speculation costs**

5. **High expense of Debt**

6. **Longer breakeven periods**

7. **High occurrence of Taxes** – Indirect assessments like VAT , Service Tax , Luxury Tax , Excise and so forth

CONCLUSION

The study concludes that's India's travel and tourism industry has enormous growth potential. The tourism industry is also looking forward to the expansion of E-visa scheme which is expected to double the tourist inflow to India. India's travel and tourism industry has the potential to expand by 2.5 per cent on the back of higher budgetary allocation and low cost healthcare facility, according to a joint study conducted by ASSOCHAM and YES BANK which interm help in expansion of Indian hospitality sector

The Government has also been making serious efforts to boost investments in tourism sector. In the hotel and tourism sector, 100 per cent FDI is allowed through the automatic route. A five-year tax holiday has been offered for 2, 3 and 4 star category hotels located around UNESCO World Heritage sites (except Delhi and Mumbai). Total FDI received by Indian hotel & tourism sector was US\$ 11.39 billion between April 2000 and June 2018. India is a large market for travel and tourism. It offers a diverse portfolio of niche tourism products - cruises, adventure, medical, wellness, sports, MICE, eco-tourism, film, rural and religious tourism. India has been recognized as a destination for spiritual tourism for domestic and international tourists.

But as we know every coin has two sides so with the vast development opportunities the hospitality sectors also have some challenges which need to be addressed

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